

Integrating species mixture to improve insights into the home-field advantage of aquatic macrophyte decomposition in a eutrophic urban lake, China

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1 **Running title:** HFA meets litter mixture

2 Abstract

- 3 1. Most estimates of ‘home-field advantage’ (HFA) effect-related decomposition in both
4 terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems focused solely on litters from single species, even
5 though HFA phenomenon relative to mixed-species litter decomposition would be
6 commonly held. The current knowledge on how litter diversity influence HFA
7 phenomenon, especially in aquatic ecosystems is very limited.
- 8 2. We conducted a reciprocal litter transplanting experiment by using leaves from three
9 different life-form aquatic macrophytes, i.e., *Trapa natans*, *Typha orientalis* and
10 *Vallisneria natans*, singly and in all possible two species combination (*T. natans*+*T.*
11 *orientalis*, *T. natans*+*V. natans* and *T. orientalis*+*V. natans*) in a eutrophic urban lake for
12 60 days with five sampling times. We used fine and coarse mesh litter bags (0.5 and 5
13 mm) to control litter accessibility to macroinvertebrates. We calculated the
14 decomposition rate, HFA effect, and the taxonomic and functional diversity of
15 associated macroinvertebrates and microbial activities for both single- and mixed-
16 species litters.
- 17 3. The significant positive HFA effect was found in both single species and litter mixture
18 decomposition, while the magnitude of HFA is higher in single species litter than in the
19 mixed-species litters and is higher in the mixed-litter from species with contrasting C:N
20 ratio (*T. natans*+*T. orientalis* and *T. orientalis*+*V. natans*) than in those with similar C:N
21 ratio (*T. natans*+*V. natans*). Notably, the macroinvertebrate abundance and richness
22 were significantly higher in both *T. orientalis* and *T. natans*+*T. orientalis* under the
23 coarse mesh litter bag treatment, evidencing the role exerted by invertebrate
24 communities in the occurrence of HFA.
- 25 4. *Synthesis.* We show that the likelihood of HFA effect (e. g., magnitude and direction)
26 response to litter diversity is common in a multispecies context and it can be weakened

27 by the non-additive decomposition that was caused by changes in litter stoichiometry
28 and by shifts in community composition of litter-associated decomposers relative to
29 species' litter mixing. Our work not only highlights the importance of both litter
30 stoichiometry and faunal community diversity in regulating the HFA response to litter
31 mixture, but also hastens the need to further test microbe specificity and potential effects
32 on the HFA effect in a multispecies aquatic ecosystem.

33 **KEYWORDS**

34 aquatic macrophytes, decomposition rate, eutrophic urban lake, functional feeding group,
35 home-field advantage, litter-associated macroinvertebrate, litter mixture effect

36 **1 | INTRODUCTION**

37 Plant litter decomposition, a key ecological process that influences organic matter
38 accumulation and nutrient cycling in all ecosystems, is generally considered to be regulated
39 by plant litter traits and decomposer communities at a local scale (Cornwell et al., 2008;
40 García-Palacios, Mckie, Handa, Frainer, & Hättenschwiler, 2016). Recently, increasing
41 evidences suggest that specific interactions between decomposer communities and plant
42 litter can regulate the rate of litter decomposition, with a consequence of accelerated
43 decomposition in its ‘home’ habitat than another habitat ‘away’ (home-field advantage, HFA)
44 in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (Austin, Vivanco, González-Arzac, & Pérez, 2014;
45 Gholz, David, Stephen, Mark, & William, 2000; Hunt, Ingham, Coleman, Elliott, & Reid,
46 1988). Although the knowledge on HFA effect-related decomposition has been well
47 developed, we still know less about the linkage of HFA to litter mixture because almost all
48 studies centred on decomposition of single-species litter (Ayres, Steltzer, Berg, & Wall,
49 2009a; Gholz et al., 2000; Gießelmann et al., 2011; Perez, Aubert, Decaëns, Trap, &
50 Chauvat, 2013; Veen, Sundqvist, & Wardle, 2015a; Li et al., 2017; Veen, Snoek, Bakx-
51 Schotman, Wardle, & van der Putten, 2019), even though HFA phenomenon relative to
52 mixed-species litter decomposition would be commonly held.

53 According to the rationale of the HFA effect in the context of single-species litter
54 decomposition, plant litter quality is one dominant control of the magnitude and direction of
55 HFA (Ayres et al., 2009b; Cornwell et al., 2008; García-Palacios et al., 2016; Gergócs &
56 Hufnagel, 2016; Gholz et al., 2000; Milcu & Manning, 2011; Veen, Freschet, Ordonez, &
57 Wardle, 2015b). A low-quality litter with recalcitrant compounds would show a greater
58 magnitude of HFA effect, due to only specialized decomposer community that resides in
59 ‘home’ habitats can decompose this kind of litter proficiently. In contrast, high-quality litter
60 with labile or nutritional compounds can be readily decomposed by almost all decomposers

61 in both ‘home’ and ‘away’ habitats, and therefore HFA is unlikely under such circumstances
62 and/or a lower magnitude of HFA effect should be expected (Ayres et al., 2009b; Li et al.,
63 2017; Veen et al., 2015b; Veen et al., 2019; Yeung, Kreutzweiser, & Richardson, 2019).
64 Specialized decomposers (i.e., invertebrates and microbes) also exerted a critically important
65 role in regulating the HFA effect via their interaction specificity with plant litters that define
66 decomposability, especially the recalcitrant fractions which were involved in the
67 decomposing process (Austin et al., 2014; Li et al., 2017; Ayres et al., 2009a). For instance,
68 the previous studies showed that the role of both invertebrates and microbial activities
69 (especially fungi) in the explanation of HFA (Milcu & Manning, 2011; Fanin, Fromin, &
70 Bertrand, 2016; Veen et al., 2019).

71 In nature, many plants can not only grow alone, but are likely to grow together, boosting
72 litter decomposition in mixed-species settings. Mixing litter of different species can lead to
73 either non-additive effect (NAE) (i.e., decomposition patterns in litter-mixes are not always
74 predictable from single-species dynamics, because of synergistic and antagonistic
75 interactions between litters from different species which are caused either by trait
76 complementarity or by inhibitory effects of diverse litter mixtures) or additive effect (AE) on
77 decomposition processes (i.e., decomposition patterns of litter-mixes are predictable from
78 component species decaying alone), which are greatly attributable to changes in litter
79 stoichiometry and subsequent shifts in community composition of litter-associated
80 decomposers (Handa et al., 2014; Heemsbergen et al., 2004; Gartner & Cardon, 2004). This
81 raises a notion that the HFA is very likely and is expected to be linked to mixed-litter
82 decomposition. While several HFA-related decomposition studies did link litter mixture with
83 HFA, the results remain uncertain, with the incidence of HFA or no HFA response to litter
84 mixing (Chomel, Guittonny-Larchevêque, DesRochers, & Baldy, 2015; Gao, Kang, & Han,
85 2016; Jewell, Shipley, Paquette, Messier, & Reich, 2015; Palozzi & Lindo, 2017). To

86 disentangle how HFA response to species mixture is of great importance for the
87 understanding of ecological processes such as decomposition that have consequences for
88 organic matter accumulation and nutrient cycling. However, to date, we still have limited
89 understanding as to how and to what extent does this interaction influence plant
90 decomposition in a multi-species context.

91 To fill this knowledge gap, we conducted a reciprocal litter transplanting experiment
92 with leaves from three different life-form aquatic macrophytes (i.e., submerged, floating-
93 leaved and emergent), singly and in all possible two species combination under two mesh
94 size litterbags (i.e., 5 mm and 0.5 mm) treatments in a eutrophic urban lake. Specifically, we
95 want to investigate the potential effect of litter mixture and its underlying mechanism on
96 HFA and whether the taxonomic and functional diversity of litter-associated
97 macroinvertebrates and microbial activity would change in response to litter mixture and, if
98 so, how the subsequent modification on HFA effect would occur. We hypothesized that (1)
99 positive HFA effect would be observed between and among the three different life-form
100 aquatic macrophytes and the magnitude of the HFA effect would be higher for low-quality
101 litter, (2) positive HFA effect would be observed in litter mixture, and the magnitude of HFA
102 effect would be higher in litter mixture of species with contrasting initial litter qualities than
103 those with similar ones, and (3) given that litter from different species was mixed, functional
104 diversity of litter-associated macroinvertebrate would change and subsequently result in
105 modification of HFA effect.

106 **2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS**

107 **2.1 | Study site**

108 The study was conducted in Donghu (East Lake) (30°33.118'N; 114°21.198'E), located in
109 Wuhan city, Hubei province, China. The Lake is the largest 'City Lake' in China and covers
110 an area of 88 km² (33 km² of water area). The average depth of the lake basin is 2.21 m and

111 the maximum is 4.75 m. The lake belongs to a warm, humid, northern subtropical climate.
112 The average surface water temperature is 18.9°C and the average rainfall is about 1160.3
113 mm (Yang, Huang, & Liu, 1999).

114 **2.2 | Macrophyte collection and litter bag processing**

115 We used three different life-form macrophytes: an emergent macrophyte – cattail or bullrush,
116 (*Typha orientalis* C. Presl), a submerged macrophyte – the eelgrass (*Vallisneria natans*
117 (Lour.) Hara), and a floating-leaved macrophyte – water chestnut (*Trapa natans* L.). We
118 collected the fresh leaves of the plant species from the study lake (Donghu) in early July
119 2018. The collected materials were cleaned with tap water to exclude any unwanted debris.
120 The *T. orientalis* leaves were cut into ~15 cm length for easy handling for drying. The
121 materials were air-dried for a week, and subsequently oven-dried for 48 h at 60° C to a
122 constant dry weight. After oven-dried, *T. orientalis* leaves were cut into ~5 cm length before
123 putting them into the litter bags.

124 We prepared three single-species *T. natans*, *T. orientalis* and *V. natans* (Tn, To and Vn)
125 and two-species mixture (*T. natans*+*T. orientalis*, *T. natans*+*V. natans* and *T. orientalis*+*V.*
126 *natans*) with the ratio of 1:1. We used two kinds of 15 cm× 20 cm nylon litter bags: litter
127 bags of 5 mm mesh size (coarse-mesh), to allow the access of macroinvertebrates, and litter
128 bags of 0.5 mm mesh size (fine-mesh), to prevent invertebrates > 0.5 mm. Litter bags were
129 filled with 10 g (±0.01) dry weight material from each species for single-species treatment
130 and 5 g (±0.01) for each species in the mixture. We prepared three replicates for all
131 treatments comprising 540 litter bags in total (six materials–three single-species and three
132 litter mixture × three sites × two mesh sizes × three replicates × five sampling times). Each
133 litter bag was coded with plastic labels to indicate plant species, site, treatment, mesh size,
134 and replicate number. On a nylon rope, we attached five clusters of litter bags (a pair of three
135 single-species and three mixtures from fine and coarse mesh litter bags) by using nylon

136 thread about 1 m apart from each other (we made sure that litter bags in each pair were 10
137 cm apart, not to overlap each other). There were three nylon ropes with five clusters of litter
138 bags for each replicate at each site (altogether 9 nylon ropes for the three sites). Weights
139 were attached to each pair of litter bags so that the litter bags remained on the surface of the
140 sediment. The nylon ropes were used to ease retrieval of litter bags.

141 **2.3 | Experimental set-up**

142 To test the HFA effect of macrophyte decomposition, we chose three experimental sites
143 dominated by *T. orientalis*, *T. natans*, and *V. natans*, respectively. The chosen sites were
144 90% dominated by the focal species and were considered as the ‘home’ habitat for each
145 species. In late August 2018, the nylon ropes with clusters of litter bags were deployed
146 reciprocally at the ‘home’ habitat of each species, and the ropes were anchored on a stone at
147 the shoreline. The habitats were 150 – 200 m apart from each other. We retrieved a pair of
148 litter bags from each rope of each site after 10, 20, 30, 45 and 60 days without disturbing
149 other samples. In total, 108 litter bags were collected at each sampling time. The litter bags
150 were placed individually in labelled and sterilized polythene bags, and brought back to the
151 laboratory in cool boxes with ice-bags. The litter bags were refrigerated at 4°C until
152 processing. Any unwanted contaminants collected along with the litter bags, such as
153 sediment soil and debris, were carefully removed. The remaining materials were oven-dried
154 at 65°C to constant dry weight for determination of the remaining dry mass (%), which was
155 used to calculate decomposition rates.

156 **2.4 | Initial litter quality analysis**

157 The oven-dried litters were ground and sieved through 0.25 mm mesh for initial litter
158 chemical analysis. The carbon content (C%) in the material was determined by rapid wet
159 oxidation-titration with $K_2Cr_2O_7$ digestion (Nelson & Sommers, 1982); nitrogen (N%) and

160 phosphorus (P%) by using an $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ digestion method (Shi, 1994). The content of N%
161 was determined by indigo blue colorimetry and P% by molybdenum antimony colorimetric
162 assay; lignin, hemicellulose, and fiber by proximate analysis via an acid detergent fiber
163 (ADF) method (Rowland & Roberts, 1994); polyphenolic substances using Folin-Ciocalteu
164 phenol reagent.

165 **2.5 | Macroinvertebrate extraction and microbial activity determination**

166 In the laboratory, the plant detritus were taken out of the litter bags before drying, and the
167 macroinvertebrates were carefully extracted with forceps, and preserved in 70% ethanol for
168 further taxonomic identification and enumeration. By using a stereo-microscope at a
169 magnification of at least 8×, macroinvertebrates were identified to the lowest possible
170 taxonomic level according to (Cummins, Merritt, & Andrade, 2005). Abundance was
171 expressed as a number of individuals per litter bag ($\text{ind} \cdot \text{bag}^{-1}$) and taxa richness was
172 expressed as a number of taxa per litter bag ($\text{taxa} \cdot \text{bag}^{-1}$). All individuals were assigned to
173 one of the following functional feeding groups (FFGs): shredders, scrapers, gathering-
174 collectors, and predators according to Merritt, Cummins, and Berg (2008). The material from
175 each litter bag was weighted to ~5.0 g (wet weight) to test microbial respiration rate. The
176 microbial respiration rate was measured after incubation (24 h) at 25°C, using an alkali
177 absorption in a closed chamber method (Wollum II, 1982).

178 **2.6 | Statistical analyses**

179 Mass remaining was expressed as a percentage of the total initial dry mass. The litter
180 decomposition rate was determined by using the exponential equation according to Bärlocher
181 (2005),

$$182 \quad M_t = M_0 \times e^{-kt},$$

183 where M_t is the litter mass remaining (g) at time 't' (day), M_0 is the initial mass of the litter,
184 and ' k ' is the litter decomposition rate constant (day^{-1}).

185 To calculate if there were any litter mixing (non-additive) effects during decomposition
186 of litter mixtures, we compared the observed rates of mass loss to the expected rates
187 calculated from the means of the component species to show litter mixing effect.

188 The HFA was calculated from the relative litter mass loss for the single-species and litter
189 mixture in each of the three sites using a method originally introduced to calculate HFA in
190 sports (Clarke & Norman, 1995) and subsequently used for decomposition data by Ayres et
191 al. (2009a) and Veen et al. (2015a). This method allows for the HFA to be disentangled from
192 site and litter effects by using the following four equations:

$$193 \quad \text{ADH}_i = \text{HDD}_i - \text{ADD}_i - H \quad \text{eqn 1}$$

$$194 \quad \text{HDD}_i = (D_{iI} - D_{jI}) + (D_{iI} - D_{kI}) \quad \text{eqn 2}$$

$$195 \quad \text{ADD}_i = (D_{iJ} - D_{jJ}) + (D_{iK} - D_{kK}) \quad \text{eqn 3}$$

$$196 \quad H = (\text{HDD}_i + \text{HDD}_j + \text{HDD}_k) / (N - 1) \quad \text{eqn 4}$$

197 where ADH_i is the additional decomposition at home for species i ; i , j , and k are litters
198 derived from plant species i , j and k , respectively; I , J and K are sites dominated by species i ,
199 j and k , respectively; D is a measure of decomposition (e.g. relative litter mass loss); HDD
200 and ADD represent home decomposition difference and away decomposition difference,
201 respectively; H represents the total HFA for all species combined; and N represents the
202 number of species. If $\text{ADH}_i > 0$, litter from species i decomposed faster than expected when
203 at home (i.e. HFA); if $\text{ADH}_i = 0$, litter decomposition at home occurred at the rate that was
204 expected (i.e. no HFA); and if $\text{ADH}_i < 0$, litter decomposition at home occurred slower than
205 expected (i.e. home-field disadvantage). We calculated ADH for each species, and ANOVAs
206 were performed on the resulting values to test for significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among
207 each species.

208 All statistical tests were performed using SPSS (Ver. 25, IBM, Armonk, NY, USA).
209 Data were checked for deviations from normality and homogeneity of variance before
210 analysis. ANOVAs and Tukey's *post-hoc* tests were performed on all significant results to
211 reveal differences among treatments ($p < 0.05$). General linear model (GLM) was used to
212 examine the effects of litter species (single and mixture), habitat ('home' and 'away'), and
213 mesh sizes (fine and coarse) on relative mass loss, macroinvertebrate abundance and richness,
214 and microbial respiration rate. Independent sample *t*-test was used to compare the observed
215 and the expected mass loss rate of litter mixture. One sample *t*-test was used to determine
216 whether litter mixing effects were significantly different from zero. One-way ANOVAs were
217 used to compare initial litter qualities of the test species, the differences between
218 decomposition rates ($k \text{ day}^{-1}$) and the magnitude of HFA between each species.

219 **3 | RESULTS**

220 **3.1 | Initial litter qualities, decomposition rate, and HFA in single-species**

221 The initial litter qualities of the three tested species were significantly different from each
222 other ($F_{2,6} = > 7.531, p = < 0.023$) except for the content of P% ($F_{2,6} = 1.947, p = 0.223$). *T.*
223 *orientalis* showed lower litter quality than other species with the lowest content of N% and
224 the highest C/N ratio, cellulose and hemicellulose content. By contrast, *T. natans* had a
225 higher litter quality than others with the highest contents of total phenol, the lowest of
226 lignin %, lignin/N, cellulose, and hemicellulose while *V. natans* had the intermediate litter
227 quality among them (Table 1).

228 The relative mass loss of the tested plant materials was significantly higher in the first
229 ten days of the experiment due to the leaching of soluble nutrient from the materials and
230 gradually slowed down throughout the whole experiment (Fig. 1). For single-species, the
231 decomposition rate ($k \text{ day}^{-1}$) of *T. natans* was the fastest from both fine and coarse mesh
232 litter bags (0.067 day^{-1} and 0.114 day^{-1}) while that of *T. orientalis* was the lowest of all;

233 0.011 day⁻¹ from fine mesh and 0.013 day⁻¹ from coarse mesh litter bags, respectively. The
234 decomposition rate of *V. natans* was intermediate (Fig. 2). According to general linear model
235 (GLM), the relative mass loss of single-species were significantly affected by litter species
236 ($F_{2,258} = 240.182, p < 0.001$), habitat ('home' vs 'away') ($F_{1,258} = 13.414, p < 0.001$), mesh
237 sizes (fine and coarse) ($F_{1,258} = 38.988, p < 0.001$), and the interaction of species and mesh
238 sizes ($F_{2,258} = 6.762, p = 0.001$) (Table 2).

239 For single-species, all the three species showed positive home-field advantage (HFA)
240 effect and the magnitudes were significantly different ($F_{5,12} = 4.811, p = 0.012$) (Fig. 3a). The
241 magnitudes of HFA effect from fine mesh litter bags were much higher than those from
242 coarse mesh litter bags; the highest value was 44.97% from the fine mesh of *T. natans* while
243 the lowest was 6.73% from the coarse mesh of *V. natans*. Although the value of HFA from *T.*
244 *orientalis* was the lowest among other species in the fine mesh (23.22%), it was the highest
245 in the coarse mesh litter bag (14.43%) (Fig. 3a).

246 **3.2 | Decomposition rate, litter mixing effect, and HFA in litter mixture**

247 The decomposition rate of the litter mixture with similar C:N ratio combination (*T.*
248 *natans*+*V. natans*) was much higher than that of contrasting C:N ratio litter combination (*T.*
249 *natans*+*T. orientalis* and *T. orientalis*+*V. natans*) from both mesh sizes except in the coarse
250 mesh litter bag from *V. natans* site (Fig. 2). According to ANOVA result, the decomposition
251 rates of all litter mixtures were significantly different in all sites (*T. natans* site: $F_{5,12} =$
252 $43.815; p < 0.001$, *T. orientalis* site: $F_{5,12} = 41.060; p < 0.001$, and *V. natans* site: $F_{5,12} =$
253 $13.950; p < 0.001$). The relative mass loss of litter mixture was significantly affected by
254 litter species, habitat ('home' vs 'away'), mesh sizes (fine and coarse) and the interaction of
255 species and mesh sizes (Table 2). For litter mixture of *T. natans*+*T. orientalis*, synergistic
256 NAEs were observed in litter mixing effect only from fine mesh litter bags while AEs were
257 observed from coarse mesh litter bags as the mixing values are close to zero. On one hand,

258 litter mixing effect of *T. natans*+*V. natans* showed antagonistic NAEs from both fine and
259 coarse mesh litter bags except in *V. natans* habitat. On the other hand, synergistic NAEs
260 were observed for *T. orientalis*+*V. natans* in all habitat from both mesh sizes (Table 3).

261 We observed positive HFA effect for mixed litter but its magnitudes were not
262 significantly different among litter mixtures ($F_{5,12} = 0.931$, $p = 0.495$). The magnitudes of
263 HFA were higher for litter mixture with the combination of contrasting C:N ratio (13.84%
264 for *T. natans*+*T. orientalis* and 10.83% for *T. orientalis*+*V. natans* in fine mesh, and 11.54%
265 for *T. natans*+*T. orientalis* and 4.86% for *T. orientalis*+*V. natans* in coarse mesh) than that
266 of similar C:N ratio combination (*T. natans*+*V. natans*) from both mesh sizes (2.26% in fine
267 mesh and 1.47% in coarse mesh) (Fig. 3b), indicating synergistic NAEs enhanced the
268 magnitude of HFA. According to GLM results, the habitat ('home' and 'away') effect on the
269 relative mass loss rate was significantly different, but higher in single-species litter ($F_{1,258} =$
270 13.414 , $p < 0.001$) than litter mixture ($F_{1,258} = 6.334$, $p = 0.013$), indicating litter mixture
271 reduced the magnitude of HFA effect (Table 2).

272 **3.3 | Associated-macroinvertebrate community and microbes**

273 During 60 days of the experiment, the abundance and richness of the associated-
274 macroinvertebrate differed among retrievals of litter bags from different habitats. In total,
275 4340 macroinvertebrates from 12 taxa with four functional feeding groups (FFGs) were
276 observed (Shredders: *Eristalis* sp., *Palaemonetes sinensis*, Gathering-collectors:
277 *Prosilocerus akamusi*, *Chironomus flaviplumus*, Scrapers: *Bellamyia purificata*, *Galba*
278 *pervia*, *Radix auricularia*, *Gyraulus convexiusculus*, *Semisulcospira cancellata*, and
279 Predators: *Cercion calamorun*, *Somatochlora* sp., *Anax panybeus*). Associated
280 macroinvertebrate abundance was much higher in *T. natans* site from both mesh sizes
281 (83.4% in fine mesh and 49.4% in coarse mesh litter bags), and the richness was much
282 higher in litter bags of *T. orientalis* from both mesh sizes (Figure 1, 2 SuppInfo).

283 In fine mesh litter bags, macroinvertebrate abundance was significantly affected by litter
284 species, habitat, mesh sizes, and their interaction in both single-species and litter mixture
285 (Table 2). The larvae of Chironomidae (Gathering-collectors) was the most abundant taxon
286 in the fine mesh litter bags reaching 80.3%, follows by scrapers (mainly Viviparidae and
287 Lymnaeidae) with 19.7 % of the total abundance, but shredders and predators were not
288 observed (Fig. 4). In the coarse mesh litter bags, scrapers (especially *B. purificata* and *G.*
289 *pervia*) were the most abundant taxa followed by gathering-collectors (especially larvae of
290 Chironomidae) (68.0% and 29.5 % of the total macroinvertebrates). Shredders and predators
291 were scarce with only 0.6 and 1.9 % respectively. Overall, both scrapers and gathering-
292 collectors were much more abundant than shredders and predators in all habitats (Fig. 4).

293 For litter mixture, the interaction of species and habitat was the greatest for
294 macroinvertebrate abundance ($F_{2,258} = 25.346, p = < 0.001$) and mesh size was the greatest
295 for macroinvertebrate richness ($F_{1,258} = 137.928, p = < 0.001$) (Table 2). When comparing
296 faunal community between litter mixtures, associated macroinvertebrate abundance was
297 much higher in the mixture of *T. natans*+*T. orientalis* from *T. natans* sites whereas that of *T.*
298 *natans*+*V. natans* was higher in *V. natans* site from both mesh sizes (Figure 1 SuppInfo).
299 The macroinvertebrate richness was higher in *T. natans*+*T. orientalis* compare with *T.*
300 *natans*+*V. natans* from all habitats except from fine mesh of *T. orientalis* site (Figure 2
301 SuppInfo).

302 Compared to single-species from both mesh sizes in all sites, the microbial respiration
303 rate was slightly higher in litter mixture, but not significantly different (Figure 3 SuppInfo).
304 For single-species, the microbial respiration rate was significantly affected by mesh size
305 ($F_{1,258} = 14.105, p < 0.001$) and the interaction of species and habitat ($F_{2,258} = 7.058, p =$
306 0.001). For litter mixture, it was significantly affected by habitat ($F_{1,258} = 6.053, p = 0.015$)
307 and mesh sizes ($F_{1,258} = 22.911, p = < 0.001$) (Table 2). The maximum microbial respiration

308 rates were observed during the early stages of the experiment, and followed by subsequent
309 decline over time. No significant differences were observed between litter mixtures, but both
310 were higher in *T. natans* site than other sites (Figure 3 SuppInfo).

311 4 | DISCUSSION

312 The generality of the ‘home-field advantage’ (HFA) effect of plant decomposition, especially
313 its effect in multi-species litter context rather than on in mono-species litter decomposition,
314 are poorly understood, particularly in aquatic ecosystems. Among a handful of HFA-related
315 litter decomposition studies in aquatic settings, the incidence of HFA showed inconsistent
316 results, with either positive or negative effect (Fenoy et al., 2016; Franzitta et al., 2015;
317 Jackrel & Wootton, 2014; Leroy et al., 2017; Luai, Ding, & Wang, 2019; Yeung et al., 2019).
318 For instance, the study on decomposition rates between *Phragmite australis* and *Fucus*
319 *vesiculosus* showed that only the macrophyte *P. australis* decomposed significantly faster in
320 the place where they occur naturally, evidencing the occurrence of HFA effect for *P.*
321 *australis* (Lopes, Martins, Rodrigues, & Quintino, 2013). Jackrel and Wootton (2014)
322 showed 24% faster decomposition rate of locally derived red alder leaf than red alder leaves
323 introduced from other riparian zones in four different rivers in the Olympic Peninsula of
324 Washington State, USA. Across the freshwater-estuarine transition zone, the faster
325 decomposition rates of *Quercus* in ‘freshwater’ and *Fucus* in ‘high salinity conditions’ than
326 others showed that higher decomposition rates occurred at their ‘home’ habitats, which
327 corroborated the occurrence of HFA (Franzitta et al., 2015). In contrast, Fenoy et al. (2016)
328 provided limited support for HFA in lowland and mountain streams between *Phragmites* and
329 *Alnus* species because the decomposition rates of both species were faster in lowland than in
330 mountain streams. Moreover, during our previous study, there was a partial phenomenon of
331 HFA between *Trapa natans* and *Myriophyllum spicatum* because only *T. natans* showed
332 HFA while *M. spicatum* showed HFD (home-field disadvantage) (Luai et al., 2019).

333 Nonetheless, the oft-cited explanation for HFA effect is not satisfactory due to partially the
334 overlooked influence of plant diversity. In the present study, we tested experimentally the
335 response of HFA to species mixture and confirmed the existence of HFA in the tested
336 conditions, and also how mixed-species litters affect the magnitude and direction HFA effect.
337 We found that if we make an analogy between our study and sport activities, our result looks
338 somewhat like the saying goes: teammates and/or partnership sometimes play a crucial role
339 in a sport stadium. A stupid partner will be a hinder.

340 **4.1 | Initial litter qualities predominantly control HFA effect**

341 As predicted by our first hypothesis, we did observe a significant phenomenon of HFA effect
342 for all single-species. However, among the three species, the magnitude of HFA effect
343 (ADH %) was the highest in the high quality litter *T. natans* from the fine mesh, but the
344 lowest from the coarse mesh, while that of the lowest litter quality *T. orientalis* was the
345 lowest from fine mesh and the highest from coarse mesh litter bags. It has been well
346 documented that the magnitude of HFA was higher for more recalcitrant litter than high-
347 quality one (Ayres et al., 2009b; Milcu & Manning, 2011; Wallenstein et al., 2013; Gergócs
348 & Hufnagel, 2016; Yeung et al., 2019) because low-quality, recalcitrant (high C/N and
349 lignin/N) litter is difficult to decompose. During the process, only a few specialized
350 decomposer community, which had a long-term ecological interaction with litter that they
351 encountered most often, can decompose these compounds (Strickland, Osburn, Lauber,
352 Fierer, & Bradford, 2009). In this study, the initial litter qualities of the tested species were
353 significantly different (Table 1). Accordingly, in the coarse mesh litter bags, the HFA effect
354 was the highest in the lowest litter quality *T. orientalis* and the lowest in *T. natans*. Further, *T.*
355 *natans* litter has lower litter quality than *V. natans* litter (higher C/N), leading to the higher
356 specialized degree in decomposer communities. Therefore, the magnitude of HFA effect of *T.*
357 *natans* was relatively higher than that of *V. natans* litter from both mesh sizes.

358 In fine mesh litter bags, HFA effect was the highest in *T. natans* and the lowest in *T.*
359 *orientalis* and (Fig. 4). One possible reason is that the decomposer communities, particularly
360 aquatic macroinvertebrates (Gathering-collector, mainly the larvae of Chironomidae) were
361 highly abundant in the fine mesh of *T. natans* in its home environment than other litters. The
362 abundance of gathering-collectors would have impact on the decomposition rate and a
363 subsequent benefit for the microbial community (Vannote, Minshall, Cummins, Sedell, &
364 Cushing, 1980). According to these results, it is likely that litter quality in association with
365 decomposer activities could be one of the main control factors for the magnitude and
366 direction of the HFA effect, particularly in aquatic ecosystem.

367 **4.2 | Litter mixture regulates the HFA effect**

368 In line with our second hypothesis, we found that positive HFA effect occurred when taking
369 into account of litter mixture, but it is not as strong as that in single-species. This was
370 partially consistent with the previous findings that HFA effect was moderated or masked by
371 mixing litters (Chomel et al., 2015; Palozzi & Lindo, 2017). Some previous studies have
372 shown that decomposition of functionally diverse litter mixture did not show synergistic
373 effect, and there was no HFA effect (Hoorens, Aerts, & Stroetenga, 2003; Chapman,
374 Newman, Hart, Schweitzer, & Koch, 2013). In this study, in contrast with the previous
375 findings, we observed synergistic NAEs in couple with a higher HFA effect from the litter
376 mixture with functionally diverse litters qualities (*T. natans*+*T. orientalis* and *T.*
377 *orientalis*+*V. natans*) than more similar one (*T. natans*+*V. natans*) from both mesh sizes. We
378 found an acceleration of decomposition rate of lower-quality litter (*T. orientalis*) when *T.*
379 *orientalis* was mixed with *T. natans* and/or *V. natans*. One possible reason might be the
380 transformation of nutrient elements from high-quality litter to low-quality litter which would
381 subsidize the microbial activities, shed by the resource complementarity theory (Gartner &
382 Cardon, 2004; Schimel & Hättenschwiler, 2007; Swan & Palmer, 2006; Gessner et al., 2010).

383 As for the role of microbial decomposers for HFA, it have been proposed that they can
384 specialize in the decomposition of certain substrates (Gießelmann et al., 2011) and that its
385 specificity and diversity divergence of a microbial decomposer community between ‘home’
386 and ‘away’ habitats will lead to the incidence of HFA (Prescott & Grayston, 2013).

387 On the other hand, we observed antagonistic NAEs for the mixture of *T. natans*+*V.*
388 *natans* except in the *V. natans* habitat with the lower HFA effect than *T. natans*+*T. orientalis*
389 and *T. orientalis*+*V. natans* under both mesh sizes treatments. The possible underlying
390 reason is that the strongly lignified leaf tissue of *V. natans* litter, which is the highest among
391 the three species, could shape high structural stability, retarding further decomposition of
392 leaf litters in the mixture causing an antagonistic effect (Perez et al., 2013). However, then
393 again, it is possible that the rapid breakdown of labile compounds from *T. natans* greatly
394 exceeded that of recalcitrant compounds (e.g., lignin) in *V. natans*, resulting in overall
395 contribution to higher decomposition rates. Therefore, the HFA effect would have become
396 less pronounced in the mixture of *T. natans*+*V. natans*. Further, in this study, the litter
397 species effect for relative mass loss in litter mixture was higher than the habitat (‘home’ and
398 ‘away’) effect (Table 2). Together, our results highlight the potential effect of litter mixture
399 on moderation of the HFA effect, as evidenced by the divergence of decomposition rate of
400 mixed litters from single-species. Accordingly, some hypothesis for single-litter
401 decomposition, such as functional breadth (FB) in which the functional dissimilarities among
402 contrasting microbial communities was proposed (Fanin et al., 2016), may not be applicable
403 to litter mixture.

404 **4.3 | Variation of litter-associated decomposers induced by species mixture** 405 **modulate HFA effect**

406 In aquatic habitats, different life-form macrophytes play crucial roles in serving as habitat,
407 refuge, shelter, and feeding sites for aquatic invertebrate communities (Brönmark, 1985).

408 Hence, it is expected that decomposer assemblages associated with aquatic macrophytes
409 singly and in combination would contribute to litter decomposition through fragmentation or
410 stimulation of microbial activity by grazing. For instance, the occurrence of HFA effect was
411 clearly associated with the decomposer communities which were specialized to decompose
412 the long-term input of litter they encountered most often (Strickland et al., 2009). Besides,
413 HFA could be explained by the functional diversity of decomposer community (Chomel et
414 al., 2015). In this study, the abundance and richness of macroinvertebrates were higher in
415 litter mixture than single incubations, particularly from coarse mesh litter bags. As a
416 consequence, the magnitude of HFA was higher in single-species than litter mixture. The
417 difference in functional diversity of litter-associated macroinvertebrate between single-
418 species and litter mixture may regulate the magnitude of HFA effect. The more diverse the
419 decomposer community, the greater reduced magnitude of HFA effect might be.

420 Compared to the coarse mesh litter bags, the abundance of gathering-collectors
421 (particularly larvae of Chironomids) was significantly higher in the fine mesh litter bags. In
422 general, gathering-collectors decompose fine particulate organic matter (FPOM) to ultra-fine
423 particulate organic matter (UFPOM; size 0.5–50 μm) by collecting organic matter
424 incorporated into the sediment from the water column (Vannote et al., 1980). This, in turn,
425 strengthens the rapid growth and high metabolic rate of microbial decomposers which may
426 allow them to exploit small resource patches and act as a source of carbon for higher trophic
427 levels (Mullin & Valiela, 1996). The microbial community structure would also modify the
428 trajectory of carbon mineralization through enzyme synthesis (Fanin et al., 2016), which
429 would accelerate the decomposition rate, as evidenced by the higher HFA effects of all the
430 species in the fine mesh litter bags than that in the coarse mesh litter bags (Fig. 3).

431 In the coarse mesh litter bags, the abundance of scrapers (especially *B. purificata* and *G.*
432 *pervia*) was the highest, followed by gathering-collectors. In general, scrapers feed on

433 UFPOM which gathering-collectors have already decomposed FPOM and attached
434 microalgal communities (periphyton) (Vannote et al., 1980). As a consequence, the positive
435 HFA effect from the coarse mesh litter bags might be attributable to the higher activity of
436 litter-associated macroinvertebrates, particularly scrapers. Additionally, the difference
437 between the magnitudes of the HFA effect among different species might be a subsequent
438 result of the difference between initial litter qualities among the tested species as the
439 aforementioned. According to GLM result, species identity exerted a more pronounced effect
440 on the abundance of associated macroinvertebrate for single-species whereas the habitat
441 showed a significant effect for litter mixture (Table 2). Overall, in agreement with our third
442 hypothesis, both the initial litter qualities and the specialized decomposer communities,
443 especially FFGs would be the controlling factors for the occurrence and magnitude of HFA
444 among different life-form aquatic macrophytes in a eutrophic urban lake.

445 **5 | CONCLUSION**

446 In summary, given the linkage of litter diversity to HFA effect, we found that there is a
447 positive HFA effect for litter mixture, the same as that for single-species, but the magnitude
448 of HFA-related mixed litter decomposition was lower than that in monoculture. Further, the
449 HFA effect was higher for the litter mixture with highly contrasting litter qualities than those
450 with more similar ones. Litter mixture with contrasting initial litter quality yielded
451 synergistic non-additive effects and the higher abundance and functional diversity of litter-
452 associated macroinvertebrates, which are responsible for the higher magnitude of HFA effect.
453 We conclude that the magnitude and direction of HFA in response to species mixture can be
454 mediated not only by changes in litter stoichiometry of the component species in a mixture
455 but also by the subsequent changes of litter-associated decomposer communities. We suggest
456 further research should emphasize to test microbial specificity and potential effects on the

457 HFA effect in a multispecies aquatic ecosystem, given that aquatic microbial communities
458 are intricately linked to ecosystem functioning such as decomposition.

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466 **AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS**

467 V.B.L. performed the field and laboratory work and analyzed the data, wrote the manuscript;
468 D.W. conceived the study, revised the manuscript critically for important intellectual content;
469 both authors gave final approval for publication.

470 **DATA ACCESSIBILITY**

471 All data used in this study and supplementary information are available via the Dryad Digital
472 Repository: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.k98sf7m33> (Luai and Wang, 2019).

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638 **Table 1** Initial litter quality characteristics of *Vallisneria natans*, *Trapa natans*, and *Typha orientalis*. Values are Mean \pm SE (n = 3).

Parameters	<i>V. natans</i>	<i>T. natans</i>	<i>T. orientalis</i>	F	<i>P</i>
C (%)	24.04 \pm 0.048	40.69 \pm 0.094	41.95 \pm 0.206	321.994	< 0.001
N (%)	3.51 \pm 0.275	3.53 \pm 0.167	2.08 \pm 0.026	13.033	0.007
P (%)	0.16 \pm 0.014	0.14 \pm 0.012	0.13 \pm 0.005	1.947	0.223
C/N	6.94 \pm 0.574	11.58 \pm 0.339	20.13 \pm 0.166	260.514	< 0.001
C/P	150.99 \pm 13.042	283.95 \pm 27.866	319.25 \pm 10.698	22.26	0.002
N/P	21.94 \pm 0.890	20.43 \pm 1.579	16.00 \pm 0.577	7.531	0.023
Lignin (%)	5.83 \pm 0.267	0.50 \pm 0.525	3.92 \pm 0.123	222.75	< 0.001
Lignin/N	1.68 \pm 0.168	0.17 \pm 0.121	1.88 \pm 0.076	75.381	< 0.001
Cellulose (%)	0.22 \pm 0.00	0.10 \pm 0.219	0.35 \pm 0.008	27.854	0.001
Hemicellulose (%)	0.20 \pm 0.001	0.14 \pm 0.549	0.27 \pm 0.009	45.895	< 0.001
Total Phenol (mg/g)	2.25 \pm 0.153	103.73 \pm 0.178	31.88 \pm 0.406	11354.22	< 0.001

639 **Notes:** Included are results of a One-way ANOVA and Tukey's HSD post-hoc test of initial litter quality characteristics.

640 Significant differences in the same parameters between the species are given by bold face p values ($p < 0.05$).

641 **Table 2** GLM on the effects of litter species, habitat, mesh size and their interactions on the relative mass loss, macroinvertebrate
 642 abundance and richness, and microbial respiration rate after 60 days of decomposition.

Source	df	Relative mass loss		Macroinvertebrate abundance		Macroinvertebrate richness		Microbial respiration rate	
		F	<i>P</i>	F	<i>P</i>	F	<i>P</i>	F	<i>P</i>
single-species									
Species (S)	2	240.182	< 0.001	16.734	< 0.001	21.496	< 0.001	0.461	0.710
Habitat (H)	1	13.414	< 0.001	1.001	0.318	0.440	0.508	0.106	0.745
Mesh (M)	1	38.988	< 0.001	8.986	0.003	135.486	< 0.001	14.105	< 0.001
S × H	2	1.350	0.261	26.475	< 0.001	0.037	0.964	7.058	0.001
S × M	2	6.762	0.001	8.391	< 0.001	11.407	< 0.001	2.258	0.081
H × M	1	0.053	0.818	0.361	0.549	1.064	0.303	0.377	0.540
S × H × M	2	1.017	0.363	21.388	< 0.001	0.107	0.898	0.381	0.683
Error	258								
Litter mixture									
Species (S)	2	13.67	< 0.001	4.523	0.012	8.751	< 0.001	2.5	0.084
Habitat (H)	1	6.334	0.013	4.414	0.037	2.104	0.148	6.053	0.015
Mesh (M)	1	87.217	< 0.001	7.012	0.009	137.928	< 0.001	22.911	< 0.001
S × H	2	0.132	0.876	25.346	< 0.001	18.261	< 0.001	2.659	0.072
S × M	2	3.546	0.030	0.688	0.503	10.865	< 0.001	0.869	0.421
H × M	1	0.263	0.608	0.001	0.972	1.841	0.176	0.009	0.925
S × H × M	2	0.801	0.450	5.15	0.006	13.072	< 0.001	0.941	0.392
Error	258								

643 Significant differences are given by bold face *p* values ($p < 0.05$).

644 **Table 3** Mean observed and expected mass loss (SE) and litter mixing effect of litter mixture of *T. natans* and *T. orientalis* (Tn + To), *T. natans*
 645 and *V. natans* (Tn + Vn) and *T. orientalis* and *V. natans* (To + Vn) from three different sites ($n = 3$).

Decomposing materials	Mesh size	Relative Mass Loss								
		<i>T. natans</i> Site			<i>T. orientalis</i> Site			<i>V. natans</i> Site		
		Observed	Expected	Mixing effect	Observed	Expected	Mixing effect	Observed	Expected	Mixing effect
Tn + To	Fine	67.12 (4.33)	62.76 (4.80)	9.01	71.48 (5.37)	63.98 (1.11)	11.73	84.14 (2.62)	80.16 (0.52)	5.01
Tn + Vn	Fine	76.90 (5.06)	83.20 (3.11)	-7.75	77.57 (2.15)	83.46 (1.64)	-7.06	77.12 (1.49)	56.42 (2.01)	37.16**
To + Vn	Fine	80.80 (1.36)	61.50 (1.67)	31.59**	74.81 (3.89)	66.33 (2.55)	12.79	74.14 (2.62)	64.84 (1.52)	14.30*
Tn + To	Coarse	78.14 (2.16)	76.62 (2.03)	2.00	78.02 (5.64)	79.76 (4.39)	-1.37	90.40 (1.37)	91.00 (1.62)	-0.66
Tn + Vn	Coarse	86.26 (1.94)	92.68 (1.32)	-6.83	82.93 (4.15)	95.32 (2.04)	-1.25	81.35 (3.18)	72.66 (1.34)	12.19
To + Vn	Coarse	84.86 (2.21)	70.17 (1.93)	21.29*	82.93 (1.64)	78.43 (4.53)	6.29	82.79 (2.23)	69.20 (0.93)	19.60**

646 **Notes:** Values of mixing effect significantly different from zero (in One sample *t*-test) are indicated with an asterisks (* = $P < 0.05$; ** = $P < 0.01$;
 647 *** = $P < 0.001$).

648 **Fig. 1** Changes in dry weight remaining percentage (%) of single and litter mixture of *T.*
 649 *natans*, *T. orientalis*, and *V. natans* during 60 days of litter decomposition in fine and coarse-
 650 mesh litter bags at different sites. Error bars indicate standard error ($n = 3$).

651 **Fig. 2** Decomposition rates ($k \text{ day}^{-1}$) of each litter type across all sites ('home' and 'away'
 652 habitats) in which it was incubated. Error bars are standard error (SE), ($n = 3$). Bars topped by
 653 different letter significantly different at $P < 0.05$ (Tukey's *post-hoc* test). Tn = *Trapa natans*,
 654 To = *Typha orientalis*, and Vn = *Vallisneria natans*.

655 **Fig. 3** The magnitude of HFA effect for each single-species and litter mixture from fine and
 656 coarse mesh litter bags. Error bars are standard errors (SE), ($n = 3$). Bars topped by different
 657 letter significantly different at $P < 0.05$ (Tukey's *post-hoc* test).

663 **b.** *Palaemonetes sinensis*; Gathering-collectors: **c.** *Prosilocerus akamusi*, **d.** *Chironomus*
664 *flaviplumus*; Scrapers: **e.** *Bellamya purificata*, **f.** *Galba pervia*, **g.** *Radix auricularia*,
665 **h.** *Gyraulus convexiusculus*, **i.** *Semisulcospira cancellata*; and Predators: **j.** *Cercion*
666 *calamorun*, **k.** *Somatochlora* sp., **l.** *Anax panybeus*)